

ANALYSIS OF SUSTAINABLE WASTE MANAGEMENT FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS (SDGS) IN MEDAN CITY

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Abstract

Completing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030 is one of the cross-cutting challenges and problems that the City of Medan is trying to solve, even if it is not necessary. They do this to control the negative environmental, economic, social, and urban effects that threaten the city, as well as to obtain the benefits that come from doing so. The purpose of this study is to analyze green behavior, green infrastructure affecting green activity and green economy in Medan City and analyze waste management in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) targets in goals 8, 1, 11 and 12. Waste that has been separated into organic (wet) and inorganic (dry) by the community should be managed by residential waste that is carried separately due to the differences in processing purposes. Organic waste, which is generally vegetables, leaves, branches and food waste, is transported to compost plants to be used as compost, while inorganic waste in the form of plastic, metal, glass, etc. is sorted based on the type of material to be sold to factories that use these goods as raw materials (recycled). This is the realization of one of the priority programs of the Medan City Government in the field of cleanliness by launching a clean market and waste management at the Lau Cih Main Market, Medan Tuntungan which produces about four tons of waste for three days, for which comprehensive waste processing is needed.

Keywords: Waste Management, Sustainable Development Goals, Waste Pickers, Recycling, Reduce, Reuse.

INTRODUCTION

North Sumatra in 2021 with a population of around 14.80 million people has an annual waste generation of 1,681,989.94 tons / year and daily waste generation of 4,608.19 tons/day [1]. Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are the basis for the government's

foothold in carrying out sustainable development. It is important to manage urban trash, which comprises both organic and inorganic wastes, in order to maintain the environment and the investments made in urban growth. The neighborhood becomes shabby and dirty, a place where pathogenic organisms such as nests of flies, rodents and other wild animals. Thus, the litter has the potential to spread the disease. Rotting litter causes an unpleasant odor and harms health.

The process of building the entire system of state administration to realize national goals [2]. One of the ideas on sustainability issues that aim to improve welfare and overcome the impacts of climate change is the concept of a green economy. Even though the green economy is mostly separate from the rest of society, it relies on human virtues to maximize the effective use of finite resources [3].

Table 1. Waste Management Achievements In 2021 In 290 Regencies/Cities Throughout Indonesia

Information	Total (Ton/Years)	Persent (%)
Waste Reduction	5.919.272,33	16,11
Waste Handling	19.251.997,78	52,4
Managed waste	25.171.270,11	68,51
Unmanaged waste	11.569.415,39	31,49
Waste Generation	36.740.685,50	

Source : [4]

Data on the achievement of waste management in 290 regencies/cities for handling waste reduction amounted to 5,919,272.33 tons/year (16.11%). The low mindset of the surrounding community, towards existing development programs, becomes an obstacle to implementation with the aim of changing the mindset of the community to one that is more concerned with the surrounding environment. People's perspective on waste should no longer view waste as a result of useless waste, but should be viewed as something that has use value and benefits.

Figure 1. 2021 Waste Generation in the Province North Sumatra

The diagram of figure1. However, the composition of garbage changes on a yearly basis as a result of adjustments in the lifestyle and economic status of the community. This is illustrated by the statistics presented above, which demonstrates that the generation of waste will increase in parallel with the increase in population. From the picture above, the highest annual waste generation is in Medan City at 622,206.89 tons. The community's desire to process their own garbage is still quite low, and this is because the community's responsibility for waste processing is not acceptable. Any form of development can only be sustainable if the waste generated by it cannot be accumulated, but is completely reused, recycled, and recovered. As a result, waste management is a cross-sectoral issue that affects and impacts multiple aspects of sustainable development, including environmental, economic, and social aspects [5]. The term "sustainable waste management" refers to the process of collecting, transporting, processing or disposing of various types of trash, managing those wastes, and monitoring those processes in a manner that does not cause harm to the environment, human health, or future generations. This comprises anything that has to do with the organization of waste management, from the production of trash to its ultimate treatment. It is essential to practice sustainability in this area so that any waste can be managed effectively and not just thrown away in landfills, as this would be an inefficient use of resources.

Figure 2. Waste Management Medan City in 2020

In addition, it focuses sekaligus memberikan dampak positif pada sistem sosial, ekonomi, dan gaya hidup pribadi individu dalam jangka pendek dan panjang. Menjaga keberlanjutan dan integritas adalah fokus utama pembangunan berkelanjutan. Dengan demikian, integritas dalam konteks ini mengacu pada pencapaian tujuan pembangunan dengan tetap mempertimbangkan kepentingan regional dan global [6]. One of the main factors in environmentally sound economic studies and scarcity factors, it is necessary to manage resources wisely and wisely [7]. Economic activity is only one component or subsystem of people's life as a system [8]. Local government must synergize to reach an agreement to make a breakthrough as meaningful solutions for creative economy actors [9].

In other words, During development, the interests of the region should not come before the interests of the entire (the interests of all stakeholders), and different systems need to coordinate with one another and help each other out in order to make progress for everyone involved.

Central, regional and local community leaders alike are increasingly calling for improvements to so-called outcast cultures. However, trash is becoming a larger problem that affects people's health and livelihoods, as well as the environment and their well-being, beyond just individuals and households. Solid waste management is critical in today's rapidly urbanizing and populating world if we are to have cities and communities that are healthy, sustainable, and welcoming to all. We are on the verge of an environmental catastrophe if we don't do something about it. People's well-being, as well as that of their communities and the environment, would be adversely affected. There are

already a number of ways to counteract this trend. It is imperative that people from all walks of life take immediate and decisive action.

INGREDIENTS AND METHODS

Research Approach: Using the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as a lens, this study examines the role of waste management in achieving the SDGs. It tries to determine which of the SDGs (1, 8, 11, 12) are most or least influenced by current waste management policies and initiatives. "Sustainable waste management is based on accomplishing the SDGs by assessing the four Sustainable Development Goals from the perspective of waste management plans and programs," the first part of the research methodology states.

Research Location: This research was conducted in Kota Medan, North Sumatra Province

Study Duration: July 2021 to April 2022.

Sample size: 223 respondents

Sample size calculation: Uses the minimum sample standard in the SEM method.

Table 2. Calculation of the Proportion of Waste Picker Samples in the Marelan Falls Landfill

No	Origin Of Waste Wickers	Total Waste Wickers	Sample Calculation	Total Sample	Total Rounded Sample
1	Kelurahan Terjun	365	= $365/504 \times 223$	161.50	161
2	Kelurahan Titi Papan	40	= $40/504 \times 223$	17.70	18
3	Kelurahan Paya Pasir	37	= $37/504 \times 223$	16.37	16
4	Labuhan Deli	29	= $29/504 \times 223$	12.83	13
5	Kecamatan Medan Labuhan	26	= $26/504 \times 223$	11.50	12
6	Pancur Batu Kecamatan Deli Serdang	7	= $7/504 \times 223$	3.10	3
TOTAL		504		223.00	223

Source: Sample Calculation Results, 2021

Subjects > selection methods:

Table 3. Sampling Method Based on Respondent Targets

Sampling Methods	Respondent
Purposive Sampling	Key stakeholders and shareholders related to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) study based on the human development index on waste management in Medan City
Probability sampling, a sampling strategy that ensures that every member of the population has an equal chance of being included in the sample, includes the simple random sampling method.	Waste sorters (scavengers and communities in landfills) in Medan City. The number of samples/respondents taken was 200 people. Umar (2004), generally the minimum sample size that must be taken in a study is based on the research design used. For this research method the minimum number of samples of 200 subjects (waste sorters) or scavengers and communities in the landfill. The research falls already represent the population.

Source: Researchers, 2022

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4. Questionnaire Calculation on Waste Utilization

No. Item	Total Item	Score	F	Total Average Score	Percentage (%)
1,2,3,4,5,6	6	SS (5)	305	1525	28,38%
		S (4)	759	3036	56,50%
		RR (3)	264	792	14,74%
		TS (2)	10	20	0,37%
		STS (1)	0	0	0,00%
Total			1338	5373	100,00%
Max Score			6690		
Average Percentage			80,31%		
Criterion			Strong		

Source : Questionnaire Processing Results, 2022

In table 5 explains that alternative approaches to waste usage and disposal have been assessed for their environmental impact. In this alternative approach, the first step is to thoroughly characterize the waste, followed by significantly reduced testing requirements to ensure quality control and integrated concise testing to identify new waste that comes from previously characterized and low-volume waste that is being considered for disposal. Disposal/storage is the first step in a process that includes collecting, intermediate, processing and finally landfilling. It has been evolved throughout time to handle common municipal waste management issues, and the underlying concept of waste management is based on this experience. A piecemeal approach to waste management is not going to get us anywhere. Reducing the rising volume of waste that must be collected, treated, and properly disposed of necessitates a comprehensive strategy. Consider all aspects of the waste management process, as well as all actors and influencers, in an integrated approach to trash management. Its advantages include (i) improved waste evaluation and management based on improved understanding of waste characteristics, (ii) contaminant estimation release in the context of waste management scenarios and anticipated environmental conditions, (iii) quality control in the context of a detailed understanding of waste characteristics, and (iv) long-term reduction of costs associated with waste testing.

Table 5. Questionnaire Calculation on Waste Sorting

No. Item	Total Item	Score	F	Total Average Score	Percentage (%)
7,8,9,10,11,12	6	SS (5)	345	1725	31,42%
		S (4)	790	3160	57,55%
		RR (3)	200	600	10,93%
		TS (2)	3	6	0,11%
		STS (1)	0	0	0,00%
Total			1338	5491	100,00%
Max Score			6690		
Average Percentage			82,08%		
Criterion			Very Strong		

Source : Questionnaire Processing Results, 2022

Table 6 means that waste sorting is included in the category of very strong because it becomes an important step in the management and recycling of waste, which allows for recovery from wasted resources. If there is one part of the complicated and difficult recycling process, it is part of separating and sorting recycled goods. Effective recycling relies on effective and efficient sorting. Separating the various elements found in the waste stream is essential to recovering valuable materials, minimizing the amount of materials sent to landfills, and allowing recyclable materials to find new purposes.

Figure 3. Illustration of the General Flow of Waste and Waste Management Costs at the Household Level in Medan City

Figure 3 indicates that it should be managed by domestic waste that has been sorted by the community between organic waste (wet) and inorganic garbage (dry). This waste should then be carried separately since the processing purpose is different for each type of waste. Organic waste, which is generally vegetables, leaves, branches and food waste, is transported to the compost plant to be used as compost, while inorganic waste in the form of plastic, metal, glass, and others is sorted based on the type of material to be sold to factories that use these goods as raw materials (recycled). This is the realization of one of the priority programs of the Medan City Government in the field of cleanliness by launching a clean market and waste management at the Lau Cih Main Market, Medan Tuntungan which produces about four tons of waste for three days, for which comprehensive waste processing is needed. DKP works closely with individuals who collect waste to collect waste from each household and transport it to garbage collection points. According to Medan City By Law No. 10/2012, the cost of collecting and disposing of waste (levy) varies based on the size of the residence and its location in the city. a monthly charge of around Rp 15,000 for households with an income level somewhere in the center.

The Role Of The Waste Management Sector In Achieving The SDGs

Taking into account the Sustainable Development Goals, which encompass a variety of aspects of urban governance. It is plain to see that the interaction and dependence between this industry and the waste management industry, which is characterized by ecologically responsible practices, are of the utmost importance. Whether they are directly or indirectly influenced by environmentally sound waste management, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) indicators that are affected by programs and plans for waste management affect the achievement and improvement of a large number of other SDG indicators.

These indicators touch on a large number of aspects of development that are vitally important. To analyze the possibilities of achieving the Sustainable Development Goals from the point of view of waste management plans and programs, given that these plans and programs support the achievement of various specific targets set out in the 1, 8, 11, and 12 SDGs, either directly or indirectly, beginning with environmental and urban development by improving the quality of life in cities, maintaining the sustainability of local communities, and reducing the negative impact that individuals have on the environment of the city.

Waste Management Plan in the **SDGs 1**. Include waste picker as informal workers in improving their economy to downplay poverty. The provision of acceptable job opportunities for everyone is complicated significantly by the prevalence of informal work. Informal labour is becoming more commonplace inside the city of Medan's trash management system. According to a framework that does not guarantee social insurance or safety standards, the informal sector in the waste management system needs to be integrated into the formal framework of the system in order to improve the working conditions of its employees and bring them in line with the rest of the system. **SDGs 8**. Incorporation of waste management systems informal into a formal system ensures improving the informal work environment and supporting economic growth opportunities. The management of waste incorporates a number of ideas that are connected to lowering output and regulating patterns of consumption. These ideas include transitioning toward an economic model that is based on recycled materials and turning garbage that can be reused into resources. It helps the manufacturing process utilize less natural resources, which is good for the environment. It requires a significant amount of self-discipline and dedication to develop a robust personality [10]. Involving the community in the development process [11]

SDGs 11 The value of the city's quality of life indicators can be increased, and the sustainability of local communities can be maintained, through integrated and environmentally responsible waste management. Integrated garbage and solid waste management systems lessen the detrimental effects human activity has on the environment in a city. **SDGs 12**. Using a model of the circular economy that is environmentally friendly ensuring that sustainable patterns of responsible consumption and production are developed and followed. Waste and waste output can be significantly cut down by adopting a "3R efficient orientation" (reducing, reusing, and recycling). The adoption of multilateral partnerships, including those with the private sector, non-governmental organizations, and local communities is one of the most important points to which the system, as a transformation from the traditional government sector to government as a partner by adopting multilateral partnerships, has become a necessity and necessary for the success of the system waste management, as well as establishing partnerships with other sectors such as industry.

CONCLUSION

It is evident that waste plans and programs have an impact on the achievement of the

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), to varying degrees at levels 1, 8, 11, and 12 of the SDGs. The goals related to improving the quality of life and health in urban areas have the greatest impact, in addition to the goals related to providing decent work for all, supporting industrialization and innovation, and improving production and consumption patterns, as well as the goals related to addressing climate change, improving life expectancy, and improving life quality. Although there are some places that don't appear to be significantly impacted by waste management plans, such as those that are related to providing a high-quality and equitable education to everyone, which is related to the establishment of institutions that are related to the issue, there are other places that do appear to be significantly impacted.

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